

Man v Machine Research Report

Game: 615875

Generated: 2026-05-24 20:59 UTC

Session conducted: 2026-05-24 18:30 to 2026-05-24 18:33 UTC

Section 1 - Game configuration

Cycles	20
Starting bank	100000
Human participants	2
Human users	The Boss Stu
Random bot Display names	On
Mimicry Trend Followers CopyProb 0.8	10
Mimicry Cautious Copiers CopyProb 0.4	10
Mimicry Momentum Chasers CopyProb 1	10
Mimicry Reverse Mimics CopyProb 0.75	10
Mimicry Noise Traders CopyProb 0	10
LSTM bots	5
LLM bots	5
LLM prompt 1	Trend-following bias: join persistent directional moves with disciplined sizing.
LLM prompt 2	Contrarian bias: fade crowd extremes when dispersion and reversal cues align.
LLM prompt 3	Risk-first allocator: prioritize downside control and low-correlation opportunities.
LLM prompt 4	Flow-aware intraday trader: react to volume/flow imbalance and short-horizon momentum shifts.
LLM prompt 5	Regime-adaptive strategist: rotate between momentum and mean-reversion based on current market regime.
Total bot participants	60
Total participants	62
Status	Completed

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Section 2 - Participant performance Top 20

Rank	Participant	Group	Equity	P/L	Trades	Win rate %
1	trend follower #3	game_bot	147977.56	+47978	7	83.33
2	trend follower #4	game_bot	139387.56	+39388	7	66.67
3	trend follower #2	game_bot	128291.87	+28292	7	83.33
4	trend follower #1	game_bot	127020.16	+27020	4	100.00
5	trend follower #8	game_bot	123571.59	+23572	6	80.00
6	trend follower #9	game_bot	122933.19	+22933	7	66.67
7	trend follower #5	game_bot	122670.76	+22671	6	80.00
8	cautious copier #6	game_bot	114658.98	+14659	13	75.00
9	reverse mimic #3	game_bot	114307.03	+14307	8	85.71
10	momentum chaser #1	game_bot	112962.23	+12962	4	66.67
11	momentum chaser #2	game_bot	112962.23	+12962	4	66.67
12	momentum chaser #3	game_bot	112962.23	+12962	4	66.67
13	momentum chaser #4	game_bot	112962.23	+12962	4	66.67
14	momentum chaser #5	game_bot	112962.23	+12962	4	66.67
15	momentum chaser #6	game_bot	112962.23	+12962	4	66.67
16	momentum chaser #7	game_bot	112962.23	+12962	4	66.67
17	momentum chaser #8	game_bot	112962.23	+12962	4	66.67
18	momentum chaser #9	game_bot	112962.23	+12962	4	66.67
19	momentum chaser #10	game_bot	112962.23	+12962	4	66.67
20	LLM bot #1	game_llm	112962.23	+12962	4	66.67

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Section 3 - CSSD Divergence chart and statistics

Metric	Participant CSSD	Asset CSSD
Mean	0.0799	0.0172
Max	0.1371	0.0275
Min	0.0001	0.0056
Peak divergence cycle	-	Cycle 17 (-0.1219)

Cycle	Participant CSSD	Asset CSSD	Divergence	Regime
3	0.0252	0.0229	-0.0023	normal
4	0.0315	0.0275	-0.0040	normal
5	0.0427	0.0200	-0.0227	normal
6	0.0960	0.0125	-0.0835	normal
7	0.0711	0.0185	-0.0527	normal
8	0.0974	-	-	normal
9	-	0.0183	-	normal
10	0.1031	0.0126	-0.0905	normal
11	0.1055	0.0204	-0.0851	normal
12	0.1088	-	-	normal
13	-	0.0257	-	normal
14	0.1113	0.0183	-0.0930	normal
15	0.1222	0.0095	-0.1128	crisis
16	0.1334	0.0130	-0.1204	crisis
17	0.1339	0.0120	-0.1219	crisis
18	0.1371	-	-	normal
19	-	-	-	normal
20	-	-	-	normal

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Section 4 - Profit/Loss balance by participant type

Participant type	Count	Average P/L	P/L %	Median P/L
Mimicry Trend Followers CopyProb 0.8	10	+23541	+23.54%	+22933
Mimicry Cautious Copiers CopyProb 0.4	10	+4112	+4.11%	+2466
Mimicry Momentum Chasers CopyProb 1	10	+12962	+12.96%	+12962
Mimicry Reverse Mimics CopyProb 0.75	10	-2957	-2.96%	-3189
Mimicry Noise Traders CopyProb 0	10	-10530	-10.53%	-13245
LSTM bots	5	+6070	+6.07%	+6639
LLM bots	5	+2287	+2.29%	+8580
Human participants	2	+907	+0.91%	+369

Section 5 - Trade share by sector

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Section 6 - Win-rate heat map by participant type

Participant type	Count	No. of Trades	Winning Trades	Win %
Mimicry Trend Followers CopyProb 0.8	10	64	50	78.13%
Mimicry Cautious Copiers CopyProb 0.4	10	117	73	62.39%
Mimicry Momentum Chasers CopyProb 1	10	40	30	75.00%
Mimicry Reverse Mimics CopyProb 0.75	10	70	45	64.29%
Mimicry Noise Traders CopyProb 0	10	163	66	40.49%
LSTM bots	5	20	15	75.00%
LLM bots	5	20	11	55.00%
Human participants	2	21	13	61.90%

Section 7 - Equity dispersion by participant type

Participant type	Count	Min	Q1	Median	Q3	Max
Mimicry Trend Followers CopyProb 0.8	10	101011.26	114497.29	123252.39	127973.94	147977.56
Mimicry Cautious Copiers CopyProb 0.4	10	96663.25	101481.91	103781.95	107152.56	114658.98
Mimicry Momentum Chasers CopyProb 1	10	112962.23	112962.23	112962.23	112962.23	112962.23
Mimicry Reverse Mimics CopyProb 0.75	10	80819.97	92982.97	98384.90	101279.14	114307.03
Mimicry Noise Traders CopyProb 0	10	75025.44	85234.18	87614.76	93172.43	109565.51
LSTM bots	5	104219.83	105159.15	106639.32	106754.28	107578.55
LLM bots	5	88466.54	88466.54	108579.94	112962.23	112962.23
Human participants	2	100368.66	100637.97	100907.29	101176.61	101445.92

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Section 8 - Sample trade log

Timestamp	Cycle	UID	Asset	Side	Qty	Price	CSSD
2026-05-24 18:30 UTC	50305	privategame:615875:mimic:trend...	EURO	buy	2475.00	2.97	0.0001
2026-05-24 18:30 UTC	50305	privategame:615875:mimic:trend...	RETAIL	buy	84.00	58.90	0.0001
2026-05-24 18:30 UTC	50305	privategame:615875:mimic:cauti...	AGRICULTURE	sell	134.00	14.69	0.0001
2026-05-24 18:30 UTC	50305	privategame:615875:mimic:cauti...	DOLLAR	buy	4633.00	0.43	0.0001
2026-05-24 18:30 UTC	50305	privategame:615875:mimic:cauti...	YEN	sell	98.00	20.32	0.0001
2026-05-24 18:30 UTC	50305	privategame:615875:mimic:cauti...	OIL	buy	50.00	39.71	0.0001
2026-05-24 18:30 UTC	50305	privategame:615875:mimic:cauti...	SP500	buy	4.00	489.97	0.0001
2026-05-24 18:30 UTC	50305	privategame:615875:mimic:cauti...	AGRICULTURE	buy	134.00	14.99	0.0001
2026-05-24 18:30 UTC	50305	privategame:615875:mimic:rever...	ENERGY	buy	98.00	59.24	0.0001
2026-05-24 18:30 UTC	50305	privategame:615875:mimic:noise...	OIL	sell	70.00	38.93	0.0001
2026-05-24 18:30 UTC	50305	privategame:615875:mimic:noise...	CRYPTO	sell	81.00	38.43	0.0001
2026-05-24 18:30 UTC	50305	privategame:615875:mimic:noise...	CRYPTO	buy	109.00	38.66	0.0001

Section 9 - Bot-type turnover

Bot type	Orders/Cycle	Avg Order Size	Buy/Sell Imbalance
Mimicry Noise Traders CopyProb 0	8.15	616.98	-21.5%
Mimicry Cautious Copiers CopyProb 0.4	5.85	369.07	23.1%
Mimicry Reverse Mimics CopyProb 0.75	3.50	624.03	40.0%
Mimicry Trend Followers CopyProb 0.8	3.20	1015.17	50.0%
Mimicry Momentum Chasers CopyProb 1	2.00	61.50	50.0%
LSTM bots	1.00	28.05	50.0%
LLM bots	1.00	49.80	10.0%

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Section 10 - Prompt effectiveness

Prompt	Participants	P/L	Win %	Drawdown %	Regime Split
Prompt 1: Trend-following bias: join persistent directional moves with disciplined sizing.	1	+12962	66.67%	13.93%	Trend
Prompt 2: Contrarian bias: fade crowd extremes when dispersion and reversal cues align.	1	-11533	33.33%	11.54%	Contrarian
Prompt 3: Risk-first allocator: prioritize downside control and low-correlation opportunities.	1	+8580	66.67%	8.80%	Risk-first
Prompt 4: Flow-aware intraday trader: react to volume/flow imbalance and short-horizon momentum shifts.	1	+12962	66.67%	13.93%	Flow
Prompt 5: Regime-adaptive strategist: rotate between momentum and mean-reversion based on current market regime.	1	-11533	33.33%	11.54%	Adaptive

Appendix A - Human placements

Participant	Overall rank	Equity	P/L	Trades
The Boss	40	101445.92	+1446	11
Stu	43	100368.66	+369	10

Appendix B - Data dictionary

Data Dictionary	Definition
timestamp	UTC timestamp of trade execution
cycleId	Market cycle identifier
uid	Participant ledger id
asset / side / qty / price	Executed order details
pnlAfter	Approx. participant equity after the trade
cssd (Section 3)	Participant-outcome dispersion: cross-sectional SD of participant equity returns by cycle
cssd_asset (Section 3)	Christie-Huang style herding metric: cross-sectional SD of asset returns by cycle

Appendix C - How to cite

How to Cite	Reference
Platform	Magar, J.S. (2026). Man v Machine: A 24/7 Human-AI Market Simulation for Behavioural FinTech Research (Version 1.7.99). Software. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20318606